

Trichoptera

- p.1 Calamoceratidae, *Anisocentropus pyraloides* FW & HW
- p.2 Hydropsychidae, *Hydropsyche "bartini"?* FW & HW
- p.3 Leptoceridae, *Triaenodes injustus* FW
- p.4 Limnephilidae, *Clistronia magnifica* FW base_04
- p.5 Limnephilidae, *Clistronia magnifica* HW base_03
- p.6 Limnophilidae, *Limnophilus rhombiens* FW_06
- p.7 Limnophilidae, *Limnophilus rhombiens* HW_05
- p.8 Philopotamidae, *Dolophilodes aequalis* FW
- p.9 Philopotamidae, *Dolophilodes aequalis* HW
- p.10 Philopotamidae, undet. FW & HW_01
- p.11 Phryganeidae, *Phryganea grandis* female FW & HW
- p.12 Polycentropodidae, *Polycentropus interruptus* HW base_07
- p.13 Polycentropodidae, *Polycentropus interruptus*, FW & HW_02
- p.14 Rhyacophilidae, *Rhyacophila fuscula* FW & HW_08
- p.15 Rhyacophilidae, *Rhyacophila lobifera* FW_10
- p.16 Rhyacophilidae, *Rhyacophila lobifera* FW base
- p.17 Rhyacophilidae, *Rhyacophila lobifera* HW_09

FW Calamoceratidae: *Anisocentropus pyraloides*

HW

FW Leptoceridae: *Triaenodes injustus*

FW

Limnephilidae: *Clistronia magnifica* (Banks)

HW

Limnephilidae: *Clistronia magnifica*

Montana

FW Limnophilidae: *Limnophilus rhombiens*

HW

Limnophilidae: *Limnophilus rhombiens*

R starts weak, bulges at hv, then strong
bulging of mp muscle, connects R with MP
MP strands recognizable, then weaker, then strong

FW Philopotamidae: *Dolophilodes aequalis*

Forewing
Tricho: PLESIO

HW Philopotamidae: *Dolophilodes aequalis*

Hindw
Tricho: Plesio

Philopotamidae: *Dolophilodes aequalis* (Smithsonian: Ali Flint)

FW Trichoptera: Philopotamidae

FW Phryganeidae: *Phryganea grandis* ♀

G. B. Wiggins

Polycentropodidae: *Polycentropus interruptus*

HW

FW Trichoptera: Polycentropodidea

Polycentropus interruptus

Rhyacophylidae: *Rhyacophyla fuscula* Walker

HW

Rhyacophilidae: *Rhyacophila lobifera*

FW

FW Rhyacophilidae: *Rhyacophila iobifera*

Rhyacophilidae: *Rhyacophila lobifera*

HW

